

Hot Tube Test : A Versatile Tool to Simulate the Oil Related Deposit Formation Tendency in IC Engines^Ψ

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The development of laboratory bench tests to simulate the performance of engine tests has emerged as a subject of major interest. In the Hot Tube Test, motor oils are tested for their oxidative stability and are evaluated in terms of the oxidation product deposit they form. This paper intends to highlight the usefulness of this method in light of the investigations made on some standard reference and commercial engine oils.

The high temperature in the ring belt area provides ideal conditions for the formation of deposits in piston grooves which reduces the effectiveness of the rings by causing ring sticking or scuffing. This leads to excessive wear and high oil consumption. It is, therefore, essential that piston deposits be restricted to a minimum in order to maintain the high efficiency of the engine. One of the most important properties of an engine oil is its ability to prevent oil-related engine deposits¹. Thus all crankcase engine oils have to be tested on standard diesel and gasoline engines before being commercialised. Caterpillar 1-G2, 1-H2, and MWM-B are some of such engine tests designed to measure the ring sticking tendency and high temperature detergency characteristics of crankcase oils. These tests are not only costly but also extremely time consuming. More so, in India limited facility exist only in IOC (R&D), IIP Dehradun and Lubrizol India Ltd.

Thus major thrust, nowadays, is given to the development of laboratory bench simulation tests to optimise and screen the formulations before subjecting them to the costly engine tests. The present communication aims at describing one of such methods Hot Tube Test for evaluating the high temperature detergency properties of engine oils, a profile of the test results, and a possible correlation with engine tests MWM-B and hence Cat 1-G2 and Cat 1-H2.

Results and Discussion

Correlation with engine test results : RL 52 (REO 203), a high reference oil for Caterpillar 1-G2, was found to be giving a merit rating of 10 at 260°. The critical temperature corresponding to 6.0 rating was established as 295°. Since this oil is a Cat 1-G2 pass oil, any lubricant giving a merit rating of ≥ 6.0 at 290° would be expected to pass this arduous engine test. In order to substantiate the findings, tests were carried out on another high reference oil RL 82/2 and the merit rating at 290° was found to be still higher (~7.5). This oil has, in fact, been reported to be superior to REO 203 in the engine test. This becomes clear from the respective reported MWM-B ratings of 65.22 for RL 52(REO 203) and 69.2 for RL 82/2.

A low reference oil for Cat 1-G2, RL 46 (REO 191) gave a merit rating of 3.5 at 290°. The critical temperature for this oil was established as 260°. Since this oil is used as a high reference for Cat 1-H2, the temperature of 260° could be fixed for evaluation of Cat 1-H2 pass oils. The MWM-B rating for this oil has been reported to be 55. It is pertinent to note that an MWM-B rating of 65 min correspond to Caterpillar 1-G2 pass and hence API-CD class of diesel engine oil. Any oil conforming to MWM-B rating of < 65 and a pass result corresponding to RL 46 (REO 191) may be termed as Caterpillar 1-H2 pass and hence API-CC category

^Ψ Younger Scientists Award (Industrial Chemistry and Chemical Engineering Section) presented to S. K. Mazumdar in the Annual Convention of Chemists 1991 held at Calcutta.

of diesel engine oils. Figs. 1 and 2 clearly indicate that the critical hot tube test merit rating vary directly as the MWM-B merit rating and is thus an effective tool in distinguishing a Caterpillar 1-G2 Pass and Fail oil.

Fig. 1. Critical temperatures for high and low reference oils for Cat 1-G2 and MWM-B engine tests.

Fig. 2. Correlation of HTT merit rating with MWM-B merit rating for some standard reference oils.

The physicochemical characteristics of the used oils also corroborate the above findings. The kinematic viscosity of the respective samples vary directly as a function of temperature of soaking. For a similar range of temperature, the viscosity rise in the superior oil is less (Fig. 3). This is but expected on account of higher build-up of oxidised material in low reference oil. This is clearly seen in the plot

Fig. 3. Increase in kinematic viscosity for different oils.

of carbonyl band intensity ($1750-1685\text{ cm}^{-1}$) as a function of increasing test temperature (Fig. 4). Comparing the carbonyl band intensity at the same temperature, it is evident that carbonyl build-up ranges as RL 46 > RL 52 > RL 82/2.

Evaluation of commercial products : Test runs were made on commercial API-CD diesel engine oils and SF/CC gasoline engine oils. Table 1 presents a detail account of this study. The results obtained therein clearly distinguish these different class of oils. The respective merit ratings at the critical temperatures established for a given class of oils, also help in screening superior/inferior oils with respect to their detergency potential. The results, thus, indicate the versatility of this technique in predicting the efficacy of an engine oil in inhibiting formation before submitting the sample for mandatory engine testing.

Experimental

The apparatus primarily comprised of a heating furnace of pure aluminium block provided with 6 through holes (dia ~ 46 mm) and thermocouple mounting holes inside and is equipped with a PID thermal control unit capable of maintaining a given

Fig. 4. Relative intensity of $\nu_{C=O}$ band as a function of temperature for standard reference oils.

test temperature within a tolerance of $\pm 1^\circ$. The oil feeding unit was so constructed that before starting a test, the engine oil of at least 6 cm^3 was held in a syringe and the automatic oil feed speed was $0.31 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ in a continued operation of 16 h or more. The piston guide accommodated 6 such syringes. The pump used a synchronous motor, parallel shaft gear box, and precision cut lead screws. A built-in overload clutch terminated pumping action.

New and absolutely cleaned glass capillary test tubes with no traces of any inside deposits were used. Heating temperature of the soaken substances varied from 240 to $300 \pm 1^\circ$. The experiments were carried out by pumping oil from syringes at a controlled rate ($0.31 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$) up the glass capillary tubes in the heating block, the temperature being controlled by eurotherm heat controllers and carrier gas(air) fed into the glass tube through calibrated

flow meters at a rate of $10 \pm 0.5 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$. The other details of the test apparatus and methodology appear elsewhere². The tubes were rated by making comparison between condition of the inner walls of the

TABLE I—HOT TUBE TEST RESULTS ON SOME COMMERCIAL CRANKCASE ENGINE OILS

Sl. no.	Oil	HTT merit rating
<i>Diesel engine oils^a:</i>		
1.	Diesel engine oil-A Proven API-CD	6.0
2.	Diesel engine oil-B MWM-B Pass, New formulation	8.0
3.	Railroad diesel engine oil-C Proven API-CD, GEN 4 (13 TBN)	9.0
4.	Railroad diesel engine oil-D Proven API-CD, GEN 4 (13 TBN)	9.0
5.	Railroad diesel engine oil-E Proven API-CD, GEN 4 (16 TBN)	-9.9
6.	Marine trunk piston engine oil-F Proven API-CD	-9.9
7.	Marine trunk piston engine oil-G Proven API-CD	-9.9
<i>Gasoline engine oils^b:</i>		
8.	Gasoline engine oil-A Proven SF/CC, 20W-40	7.0
9.	Gasoline engine oil-B Proven SF/CC, 20W-40	8.5
10.	Gasoline engine oil-C Proven SF/CC, 20W-40 (diff VI improver)	7.5

^aHTT merit ratings at 290° .

^bHTT merit ratings at 260° .

tubes through KES : 07-803 limit card. A colourless transparent condition was graded as 10 and a black opaque condition as 0. Further 9 grades were given between 0 and 10. A critical temperature was established. The used oils were analysed for changes in kinematic viscosity and estimation of carbonyl component with respect to fresh oils. The infrared analysis was carried out by spectral recording and calculation of integral band intensities.

High reference oil from Komatsu was run for the standardisation of the instrument. The ratings for the tubes at 295° were found to be 6.0. This conformed well with the values reported with stan-

ard API-CD oil for evaluation of Komatsu factory fill oil.

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